

HO CHI MINH THOUGHT ABOUT PROMOTING THE ROLE OF THE PEOPLE IN PROTECTING THE SECURITY, ORDER

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Abstract: During his lifetime, President Ho Chi Minh was very interested in promoting the role of the people in protecting security, order. Research shows that Ho Chi Minh thought on promoting the role of the people in protecting security and order is a comprehensive and in-depth system of views on the objectives, content, and methods promote the role of the people in crime prevention and control and violations of the law. Carrying out multiple demonstrations, Ho Chi Minh's thought has theoretical value and practical orientation. Researching, searching, understanding, and clarifying the content of Ho Chi Minh's thought as a basis to apply it to the work of promoting the role of the people in security protection and self-defence in Vietnam is an established issue now.

Keywords: Ho Chi Minh Thought; people; Security, Order.

I. INTRODUCTION

Ho Chi Minh's thought on the role of the people in protecting security and order is the result of the inheritance and development of the nation's fine traditional cultural values, absorbing the cultural quintessence of mankind, applying and developing creatively Marxism-Leninism in specific historical conditions of Vietnam. The source of Ho Chi Minh's thought on promoting the role of the people in protecting security and order is the nation's tradition of respecting the people. Along with that, the Marxist-Leninist theory on the role of creating history is the worldview and methodology, helping Ho Chi Minh have a deep awareness of the great role of the masses in the development of history, revolutionary career in general and in the cause of security and order protection in particular. On that basis, he affirmed: "Revolution is a common matter of the people, not a matter of one or two people" [1, p.283].

II. CONTENTS HO CHI MINH THOUGHT ABOUT PROMOTING THE ROLE OF THE PEOPLE IN PROTECTING THE SECURITY, ORDER

2.1. Ho Chi Minh's thought about role of the people in protecting the security, order

Explaining the role of the people in protecting order and security, Ho Chi Minh said that: The people are a large group of people with enormous strength, the source of all strength to ensure victory. benefits of the cause of security and order protection. In Ho Chi Minh's thought, the people are the largest force, distributed everywhere, with tens of millions of eyes and ears like a picture of heaven, a hammock without a conspiracy, activities of criminals and criminals. Violations of the law can pass. Expressing this thought clearly, in a letter to comrade Hoang Mai, Director of the Public Security Department of Zone XII, Ho Chi Minh assessed: "Our people have tens of millions of people, tens of millions of eyes, ears, hands and feet. . If you know how to rely on the people, anything will be done" [2, p.498]. In another time, he emphasized: "With tens of thousands of eyes shining, hundreds of thousands of ears listening, the crooks and thugs will show their faces and will

have to reform under the great force of God. the masses" [6, p.77]. To clarify the great role of the people in protecting security and order, Ho Chi Minh gave a very intuitive and effective example. He said: "I give you an example: How many policemen are there? Whether there are a few thousand or five seven thousand, that force is still very few beside the people's force. Five thousand people have only 50,000 pairs of eyes and 50,000 pairs of hands. How can there be tens of millions of pairs of hands, tens of millions of pairs of eyes and ears" [4, p.270]. Understanding the role of the people, therefore, Ho Chi Minh came to affirm: "When the people help us a lot, we will succeed a lot, help us a little, we will succeed little, help us completely, we will win complete victory." complete" [4, p.270]. From here, Ho Chi Minh had an admonition: "Preserving order and security is first and foremost the job of the police, army, and police. But our government is a democratic government, no matter how big or small, we must rely on the people's forces to serve the people's interests. The maintenance of order and security must rely more on the initiative and force of the people" [6, p.77]. Understanding the great role of the people, in the process of leading the revolution, Ho Chi Minh often asked police officers and soldiers: "Must be close to the people, rely on the people's forces, and stay far away from the people. If you leave the people, you won't be able to do anything with any ingenuity" [7, p.260]. He reminded: "Being a police officer must make the people believe, the people love, the people support. Only by relying on the people can the police fulfill their duties well. People have millions of eyes and ears, it is difficult for the enemy to hide. If in their work, the aunts and uncles are supported by the people, making the people believe, obey, and love the people, then they will definitely succeed. To do so, one must cultivate revolutionary morality, and also fight against individualism" [9, p.223]. Because, according to Ho Chi Minh, the people are a solid foundation for the specialized forces to protect security and order to successfully complete their tasks.

2.2. Ho Chi Minh's thought about goal of promoting the role of the people in protecting the security, order

In Ho Chi Minh's thought, the goal of promoting the role of the people in protecting security and order in order to practice democracy, liberate the people's intelligence, help the people to clearly show their role and mobilize mobilize synergy to protect security and order. Born and raised in the context of the loss of his home and country, directly witnessing the misery of the nation, the people's lives were extremely miserable, Ho Chi Minh soon understood the essence of colonialism and feudalism. oppression, exploitation, murder. People soon realized that in order to cover for "rotten medals", colonialism and imperialism often proclaimed flowery slogans "civilization", "freedom, equality, fraternity". However, the truth behind that, in each policy, colonialism is directed towards the goal of oppression, exploitation, enslavement, stupidity, oppression and terrorism to restrain the resistance of the Vietnamese people.

In the field of security and order protection, Ho Chi Minh is aware that this is an indispensable and objective need of human society. Experiencing practical research activities in many countries around the world, he realized that colonial and imperial regimes also had activities to protect security and order. However, protecting security and order of the colonial and imperial regimes aimed to protect the interests of the few, because the interests of the ruling class were primary, not to maintain security and order. for the vast majority of the people. Even to protect their interests, they also intensified terrorist activities to make the peoples of the colonial countries lose their will to fight and protest. To expose the true face of the colonial regime's security and order protection activities, Ho Chi Minh concluded: "The imperial police are the imperial claws to oppress the majority of the people. I'm sure you guys also remember that they are buffalo-headed and horse-faced people" [4, p.269].

In Vietnam, Ho Chi Minh believes that protecting security and order is an important job. The person who soon formed the idea that after the revolution was successful, a new security and order would be built that was completely different in nature from the security and order created by the colonial and feudal regimes. build. That security and order must be based on the great strength of the people, with the people as the foundation, towards the goal of practicing democracy, for the people, liberating the people's intelligence, and helping the people to understand clearly the role of the people. the role of master and master in protecting security and order. That's why, right after the August Revolution succeeded, the fledgling government belonged to human hands, and he repeatedly called for quick measures to protect security and order. Ho Chi Minh requested: "We must make every effort to maintain security and order" [8, p.369]; Must "maintain social order and security, especially in cities, must do well" [12, p.169]; "Everyone must participate in maintaining security and order" [10, p.48]. Ho Chi Minh requested: "We must continue to strengthen national defense, suppress saboteurs, and maintain security and order for the people. Because of the above, it gradually improves the lives of people from all walks of life, making our people well fed, warmly clothed, healthy and literate" [7, p.304]. To achieve this goal, he requested: "The army, police and militia should continue to promote the tradition of brave fighting, strengthen national defense, and protect order and security" [10, p. .389].

2.3. Ho Chi Minh thought about content of promoting the role of the people in protecting the security, order

Firstly, promote the role of the people in preventing crime and violations of the law

Ho Chi Minh always attaches importance to promoting the role of the people in the work of fraud prevention and security. People who understand fraud and security are an important front, contributing to the success of the revolution. Therefore, he asked the revolutionary forces to always explain and train the people, from old people to young children, to know how to prevent fraud and keep secrets. According to him, if you do not know how to rely on the people and promote the role of the people in keeping secrets, then secrets can only be kept partially. To clarify this issue, he admonished: "Like all other jobs, the defense of security must rely on the patriotism and force of the people. We must propagate and explain to the people to understand, so that the people can help in this work" [7, p.263].

Along with that, Ho Chi Minh also attached great importance to promoting the role of the people in raising vigilance and preventing enemy sabotage. He pointed out: "Now the enemy is trying his best to find ways to sabotage us, because he doesn't want us to succeed" [6, p.444]. Therefore, the requester must always be alert and proactive in formulating effective and proactive crime prevention measures. He said: "Be very vigilant, the room is confidential... Beware that this is not only the aunts and uncles, or only the party, but it must be done so that the people must also have a sense of it. stay alert" [6, p.444]. To do this well, he called: "All our people from the South to the North, from the cities to the countryside, must always raise their vigilance, and everywhere must be ready to take precautions like during the resistance war. Wherever America's "special" minions go, they will fall into the net of our people's "heaven and earth" [10, pp.142].

Second, promote the role of the people in detecting crimes and violations of the law.

Ho Chi Minh understood that the plots and activities of criminals were very dangerous and malicious. In order to be easy to operate, they always find ways to hide and hide in order to resist the detection, prevention and struggle of specialized agencies. Therefore, according to him: "It is not the police, soldiers or cadres who see all its sabotage plots, but ask the people to see it" [6, p.445]. Because the force of the people is extremely large, widely distributed, the people have thousands of eyes and ears, making the criminal gangs unable to overcome but will have to "come out". Expressing this point clearly, Ho Chi Minh assessed: "Millions of people's ears and eyes have become pictures of "heaven and earth", so the secret agents cannot escape" [4, p.53]

Aware of the immense power of the people, Ho Chi Minh requested that in protecting security and order, the people must promote the role of the people in detecting plots, methods and activities of criminals. Ho Chi Minh advised: "Technical issues in police work are also needed, but the most important issue is education and propaganda for the people, in order to better manage the people's ears, eyes, mouth, and how the people do it. help the police to detect the enemy and hide our things from the enemy" [12, p.140]. Along with that, Ho Chi Minh also reminded: "Intelligence, like everything else, must rely on the people. The eyes and ears of an intelligence person are limited. People have tens of millions of eyes and ears. Anything they can hear, can see, can know" [3, p.192].

Third, promote the role of the people in fighting crime and violations of the law.

Ho Chi Minh clearly expressed his request to promote the role of the people in fighting crime and law violations in many speeches and articles. Ho Chi Minh affirmed: "... maintaining order and security in society is very important. Soldiers, police, militiamen and self-defense officers must consider that as their main task. Must do well. And all the people must be in charge, because let it destroy the whole people will suffer" [10, p.265]. People often ask to "more closely unite, raise vigilance further, pay attention to prevent vandals, maintain order and security" [7, p.266].

Not only focusing on promoting the role of the people in fighting various types of crimes and law violations committed in society, Ho Chi Minh also attaches great importance to promoting the role of the people in the fight against the law. fight against illegal acts committed by corrupt and corrupt officials and party members within the political system, especially embezzlement, wastefulness and bureaucracy. He reminded: "As the owner, the people must fulfill the duties of the owner, must manage the capital well, that is: ... fight corruption and wastefulness, make the capital prosperous, and implement the beauty of the capital city. customary customs, need, thrift, integrity, righteous" [7, p.266]. In another time, Ho Chi Minh requested: "Every citizen, each agency needs to resolutely fight against embezzlement and waste" [6, p.298].

2.4. Ho Chi Minh thought about methods to promote the role of the people in protecting the security, order

In order to promote the role of the people in protecting security and order, according to Ho Chi Minh, on the one hand, the people must constantly try and actively participate in the protection of security and order. On the other hand, Ho Chi Minh believes that it is necessary to use the right, creative and appropriate method. First of all, according to Ho Chi Minh, it is necessary to actively propagate and educate the people to understand their rights and obligations in protecting security and order. Ho Chi Minh requested: "The police must always help, organize and educate the people, make all people their assistants, and form a network of people's police. Only then will the work be fruitful" [9, p.154]. Second, according to Ho Chi Minh, it is necessary to do a good job of mass mobilization. He said: "The people's force is very large. The critical mass agitation. Mass Mobilization things are less bad. With good publicity, everything will be successful" [3, p.234]. At the same time, Ho Chi Minh requested to focus on building and consolidating people's organizations very well and firmly. He repeatedly taught: "We must make every effort to strengthen the people's government and strengthen the people's organizations in the localities. Because if the people's government and local people's organizations are loose, the policies of the Party and the Government are not implemented properly. Therefore, it is necessary to strengthen the people's administration and strengthen the people's organizations, in which special attention must be paid to the organization of the police and the guerrilla militia, because the police and militia have the duty to maintain order. security in the locality" [7, p.612].

III. CONCLUSION

In summary, Ho Chi Minh's thought about promoting the role of the people in protecting the security, order has been studied and understood with many published scientific works. To further clarify the content of Ho Chi Minh's thought, we have focused on using scientific research methods and systematizing Ho Chi Minh's thought on promoting the role of the people in security protection. order into a system of views including Ho Chi Minh's thought on the role of the people in protecting security and order; Ho Chi Minh's thought on the goal of promoting the role of the people in protecting security and order; Ho Chi Minh's thought on methods to promote the role of the people in protecting security and order.

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